

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B198
Date: 12 May 2006
Take Off: 10:57:31
Landing: 15:44:45
Flight Time: 4h47m14s

Campaign: ICEPIC
Trials Instructions:
Operating Area: Wales

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 2	Clare Lee	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	Cloud physics / chem/ccm2	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
7	Miss Scientist 1	Chawn Harlow	Met Office
8	CPI	Hazel Jones	Manchester University
9	AMS	Jonny Crosier	Manchester University
10			
11			
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15			
16			
17			
18			

Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b198
 Date: 12 May 2006
 Project: icepic
 Location: Wales

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
103103		cgps	0.26 kft	125	b198cgps.log started
103214		inu	0.26 kft	125	to nav
105731		T/O	0.28 kft	210	egtc
112640		jw	6.0 kft	179	zero
112657		nev	6.0 kft	179	cal
115610	120527	Profile 1.0	10.0 - 20.0 kft	261	
120012		Video	14.3 kft	262	#1 dfc #2 ffc
120707		tw	20.0 kft	283	status on
122628	124336	Profile 2.0	20.0 - 4.0 kft	325	
124522	124852	Profile 2.1	4.0 - 0.98 kft	133	1000ft qnh 1015
124853	125853	Run 1.0	0.98 kft	144	1000ft qnh 1015
125854	130239	Profile 3.0	0.98 - 4.2 kft	144	
130350		JW	4.3 kft	036	zero
130400		nev	4.3 kft	030	cal
130416	131415	Run 2.0	4.3 kft	036	
131549	131743	Profile 4.0	4.3 - 5.9 kft	185	
131743	132712	Run 3.0	5.9 - 7.0 kft	172	
131859		!	6.4 kft	170	climb to 7000ft t0 0C
131920		!	6.9 kft	170	restart run
132932	133803	Run 4.0	8.5 kft	021	
133240		video	8.5 kft	023	#3 dfc #4 ffc
134038	135015	Run 5.0	9.5 kft	163	
134737		!	9.4 kft	216	alarm nev total water
135141		!	11.0 kft	257	nev tw off (alarm)
135241	140334	Run 6.0	11.1 - 11.0 kft	053	
135632		!	11.0 kft	030	ffc iced up #4 rfc
141437		!	7.0 kft	016	descent to 6000' to c lear ice
141712	142353	Run 7.0	11.5 kft	169	
142433		!	9.7 kft	231	descend to deice
142951	143816	Run 8.0	13.0 kft	076	
144022	145317	Profile 5	13.0 - 0.99 kft	262	
144125		DITM	11.9 kft	263	Deice on
145503	151032	Profile 6.0	2.7 - 20.0 kft	105	
150407		!	11.5 kft	106	fm pc crash & HORACE autoreset
150550		!	13.6 kft	107	turb probe pitot now ok
150859		!	18.1 kft	109	nev total water now o
150959		!	19.5 kft	107	DITM dead since 1440
151033	152032	Run 9.0	20.0 kft	109	
151308		JW	20.0 kft	115	zero
151322		nev	20.0 kft	116	zero
154445		Land	0.31 kft	213	egtc

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MB INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

B198 Track 12-MAY-06

Flight No: B198

Date: 12th May 2006

Trial objectives:

To investigate the development of ice-phase and precipitation in Cu over the UK.

Location:

In developing Cu clouds over Central S.England or Wales (suggest a rectangular box with NW corner at 54deg N, 05deg 30min W and SE corner at 50deg 30 N, 01deg W)

Weather:

Either individual, or groups of Cu cloud forming predominantly over land. Evolving clouds may also be tracked over the sea.

Special requirements:

Key temperature levels for cloud penetrations are 0, -3, -6, -9C then colder as reqd. If operating near Chilbolton radar, relay range/bearing of target clouds to "Radsearch" (130.575 MHz)

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Cranfield at 12:00L.
2. Transit to the operating region at FL200 and identify suitable area for operations (40mins).
3. Perform stepped profile descent from FL200 to minimum permitted altitude at 1000ft/minute (70mins).
4. Perform a SLR below cloud for 10minutes in a direction determined by the mission scientist (85mins).
5. Turn onto reciprocal heading and perform a SLR at 500ft below cloudbase for ten minutes (100mins).
6. Ascend to around the 0C level or 500ft below the cloud top (110mins).
7. Perform a penetration with wings level through the cloud (115mins).
8. If a single cloud is large and clearly identifiable and the cloud is continuing to develop, make a reciprocal turn while ascending by ~1000ft (-3C in temperature) and repeat the cloud penetration several times (150mins).
9. If the cloud is not large or discrete, then proceed successively to the next visible cumulus cell, and repeat the penetrations at approximately 0C for a 10minute interval. Perform reciprocal turn while climbing by intervals of -3C and repeat 10minute runs (150mins).
10. Continue 8 and/or 9 as time permits (250mins).
11. Finish with a profile ascent from minimum permitted altitude to FL200 or 1000ft above highest cumulus tops (whichever is higher) at 1000ft/min.
12. Transit to Cranfield and land (17:00L).

Note) – target clouds should be continuing to develop – look for rising cloud tops and solid, sharp-edged cloud boundaries. If red echoes show on the aircraft radar, or cloud top is decreasing, or cloud becomes heavily glaciated (diffuse boundaries) then move on to next cloud

B198 -- Mission Debrief
ICEPIC sortie
Date of mission: 12/5/06
Mission Scientist: Chawn Harlow

After initial difficulties with routing by air traffic control, who had apparently not been briefed of our intentions despite the best efforts of the pilots, we arrived at Chilbolton approximately 40 minutes after the 1100 Z take off. As there was very little sign of cumulus development, we continued on to Devon and Cornwall. There were a couple of large cells there that were a bit too developed as they were already approximately 3000 ft thick, and the peninsula was blanketed with stratocumulus making diagnosis of development of early stage cumulus difficult. As was previously planned, we continued on to mid-Wales where we found a line of juvenile cumulus aligned parallel to the Welsh mountains in a general N-S direction.

We started at 1226 Z with a clear air profile down from FL 200 to 1000' over the Aberporth Range to sample the air upwind of the developing Cu. A 10 minute run was carried out at 1000' over the sea as we approached the southern end of the operating area from the northwest. As the terrain limited our minimum altitude below cloud base, we flew our next run at 4300' which was near cloud base. Runs followed at FL 070, FL 085, FL 095, FL 110, FL 115, and FL130 where the dry air deiced temperatures were approximately 1, -3, -5, -9, -11, and -15 °C, respectively. The cumulus clouds continued to develop during and after the sortie with cloud tops typically 200' – 2000' above run altitude and with duration of penetrations increasing with altitude. After the runs at FL 110 and FL 115, descents were necessary to approximately FL 060 in order to deice the instruments. After the run at FL 130, a clear air profile was performed back down into Aberporth. Then a profile climb was performed back up to FL 200 to sample the air above the clouds. By that time the cloud tops were approximately FL 250 and rising. We found a clear area above a saddle point in the cloud tops that occurred between two coalescing Cu cells. After a 10 minute run at FL 220, we descended for the transit back to Cranfield.

This was a very successful flight leading to multiple penetrations of developing cumulus clouds. It is unfortunate that the following instruments were not available: SID-2, CCN, CVI, INC and ADA. However, I believe that the other key instruments listed in the project brief were available.

Instrument problems:

Rosemount (deiced) packed in during R6 at FL110
Nevzerov suspect
Turbulence probe iced up during runs at FL110 and above
FFSSP failed intermittently when the heater was on

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.198**..... Date 12/5/06 Name Chawn, Harlow age 1 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1100	T/O				T/O Cranfield
1105		FL100			Advice given by Phil Brazner over SATCOM that convection inhibited by Ci over Chub + S. Wales. Expect Con over N. Wales + Devon + CW
1120					Quite hazy below
1122			246		Ascending to FLO60 - diverted by ATC
11:32		FL055			" " "
11:37					Over Chibolton
11:41		FL100	259		Change heading & hgt Chibolton reports no Cu to west
11:52					Moderate Turbulence
1156	PL				Climb to FL 200
					Freezing lvl ~ 570 mb
1201		FL160	260		Cu tops below
	PL	FL200			End
1207					Off to Snowdonia
					SCu everywhere; no isolated Cu
1225					Many Cu of interest in W Wales
122628	P2.0	FL200	122		Profile into Aberpoth (item 3)
					West of Cu above

Turb.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B** ¹⁹⁸..... Date ^{12/5/06}..... Name ^{Harlow}..... age ² of ⁴.....

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
124336	P2.0	4000'			Interrupt (Massive increase in)
124522	P2.1	4000'			Start (aerosol on AMS)
124852	P2.2	1000'			End Visibility limiting min alt.
"	R1 st	1000'	123		Run to sample upwind of
125854	R1 ^{End}	1000'	123		operating area.
"	P3.0	1000'- 4300'	112		Alt. limited by terrain
	P3.0				cloud base ~ 3000'
130416	R2S		157		Run "below" cloud
1312					cloud penetration
131415	R2E				
131549	P4.0	4300'- 6000'			
131743	R3 ^S	6000'	157		Opting for B plan
131920	R3 ^S	7000'			Readjust to 1°C
					In cloud run
132712	R3E	7000'			FFSSP dropping out/in
132932	R4 ^S	8500'	091		500'-1000' below top
					-3°C
					Probe w/ Cloud Phys.
					FFSSP drops out when heater
					on; operator turning off heater
1335					Enter big cloud
					2000' below cloud top
1336					100' " " " "
133803	R4E				CPI and Cloud Phys seeing
					different mean size

Turb.
Turb

Turb.
in
cloud

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.198**..... Date 12/5/06..... Name Harlow..... age 3 of 4.....

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
134038	R5S	FL095			200' below top -5°C
135015	R5E	FL095			1000' below top (13:43)
					2000' " " (13:45)
					" " " (13:46:45)
					Early stage (13:48) 2000' BCT
135241	R6S	FL110	105		-8.5°C
					500' BCT 13:53:45
					" " 13:54:26
					-9.88°C 13:55
					1000' BCT "
					" " 13:58
					2000' BCT 13:59
					Large particles on CPL
					-10.1°C TP -7°C
140334	R6E	FL110			Turb probes iced; FFC iced
	R7S	FL115			Interrupt to de-ice 14:11
		FL060			FFC clear 14:13
		"			Turb. probes clear 14:13:40
141712	R7S	FL115			2500' BCT 14:18:35
					Neph. TWC packed in
					FFC iced up again
142323	F7E	FL115			Interrupt to De-ice

TW

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.198**..... Date **12/5/06**..... Name **Harlow**..... age **4** of **4**.....

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
142951	R8S	FL130			
					1000' BCT 14:32:30
143617	R8E	FL130			-15°C
144032	P5S	13000 -1000			
145317	P5E				
145503	P6S	1000 -FL200			
1506					Climb rate inc to 1500'/min
					Big Cb's where we previously sampled Cu
151033	P6E				
11	R9S	FL200			
152032	R9E	11			End of Science
					Instrument Status Check:
					Core - Rosemount Packed in
					- Newzeroy suspect - Turb probe OK
					Cloud Phys - FFSSP intermittent Failure
					CPI - Fine minas ice up
					AMS - Good data early on

Mission Scientist's Log

MISSION SCI 2.

Flight No **B.198** Date **12/5/06** Name **CLARE LEE** age **1** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
105731					Take off from Cranfield.
		FL100			Transiting towards Chilbolton
115610	P1↑	FL00			Climbing higher to get a good
120527	P1end	FL200			look at cloud below.
					All convective activity is
					producing STC - no isolated
					cells observable.
122528					Suitable W cells identified.
					Manoeuvring towards them.
122628	P2↓	FL200	325	52°6'N 1 3°54'W	Profile descent into area.
124100		6200ft.			AMS recording increase in
					aerzol. - jump between
					8000 → 7000ft.
124336	P2int.	4000ft.			Interrupt profile descent.
124522	P2int.	4000ft.			Recommencing profile descent.
124852	P2.1end	1000ft.			
	(R1.0	1000ft.			Run at 250ft. over sea.
125854	(R1.0end	1000ft.			
	(P3.0↑	1000ft.			Profile climb.
					Heading towards W cells over land.
130239	P3.0end	4300ft.	145		Hazy around.
130416	R2.0	4300ft.	037		T 8.3°C, T _D 1.2°C
					in clear sky parts. Cloud base
					below safe altitude.
					No cloud particles measured.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

MISSION SCIENTIST 2.

Flight No **B.198**.....

Date **12/15/06**.....

Page **2** of **6**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
131210		4300ft.	022		Turbulence
131415	R2end				Run ended
					Turning reciprocal forwards to cell
131549	P4↑	4300ft.			Profiling to 6000ft ~ T=0. N.B. All good cells in airway - not possible to work in.
131743	R3	6000ft.			T = 3.5° Readjusting to 7000ft. to get T=0 no profile.
131820	R3	7000ft.			T = 1.05°C Run 3 restarted.
132000					In cloud.
132030					Out of cloud no particles / drops measured.
132140					In cloud.
132230					Out of cloud SID seeing small particles.
132305					In cloud T = 1°C.
132320					Out of cloud.
132400					CPL + cloud phys → large blobs. T = 0.84°C, T _D = -1.53°C.
132610					In cloud
132640					Out cloud T = 1.28°C, T _D = -3.3°C
132712	R3end	7000ft.			End of run.
			189		Climbing to 8500ft. for diff. Temp. + turn tonight.
132932	R4	8500ft.			T = -3°C, T _D = -5°
133027					In cloud for 5secs.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.198**
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 Date **12/5/06**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
133105		8500ft.			In cloud. tops ~ 1000ft above. T = -3.5°C, T _D = -5.1°C 2D + CPI seeing out of cloud.
133210					CPI seeing ice.
133250					Out of cloud. Manoeuvring to next cell.
133450					In cloud. (billowing) tops ~ 2000ft above T = -3.5°C, T _D = 0.46°C
133540					Out cloud
133608					Series W tops ~ 1000 → 2000ft. 1st one ~ 500ft tops, for few secs.
133642					Next cloud. CPI small + crystals 15µm droplets Cloud phys upto 3000µm blobby.
133803	R Lead	8500ft.			End of run + climbing (non-proble)
134038	RS.0	9500ft.	8000		
134058					In cloud ~ 200ft below top.
134108		9500ft.			Out of cloud, T = -5.15°C, T _D = -10°C Manoeuvring towards next cell.
134230					In cloud
134240					Out "
134320					In cloud ~ 1000ft below top. T = -5.2 T _D = -5.5
134408		9500ft.			Out cloud. T = -4.8°C, T _D = 8.9°C

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.198**.....

 Date 12/5/06.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
134450					In cloud, v. turbulent. ~ 2000ft ^{above} tops
134500					Out cloud.
134657		9500ft.			In cloud tops ~ 2000ft above. smooth T = -7.27°C, T _D = -3°C
134750					Out of cloud.
134809					In cloud ~ 2000ft below top. T = -6°C, T _D = -5°C
43					Going through sequence ~ 45s each. All in early stages. increasing in altitude
135050	R5end.				Turning back towards
135424	R6	11000ft.			In cloud ~ 500ft below tops. T = -9°C, T _D = -10.7°C
					In + out of sequence. FFC iced up. ^{cloud tops} probest turbulence probes all OK. seem to be getting supercooled water + ice mixed - variable.
135830					Heading towards more developed cells ~ 2000ft below tops. CP1+2D seeing much larger
140111					~ 2500ft below cloud top. T = -10.7°C, T _D = -8°C.
140334	R6end	11000ft.			In clear sky. M/S laptop at of power. plugged back in OK.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.198**.....

 Date **12/5/06**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
141109	R7	FL115			Turbulence profile showing signs of icing - descending to 6000ft. to melt ice.
141400		6000ft.			Increasing back to recurrence flying through CW tops.
141712	R7	FL115	160		In cloud top ~ 1000 → 2000ft above
141820					(TWC Nav. failed.) T = -8.8°C, T _D = -8.0°C
					lots turbulence.
					ETC freezing up.
					CP1 + 2D seeing Hob shapes rather than pristine crystals. + supercooled water.
142320					Out of cloud. Probes + inlets icing. descend to warm up.
142353	R7 end.				
142615					Ascending again.
142951	R8	FL130	077		
143210					In cloud ~ 1000ft below top. T = -14.6, T _D = -7.7
143535					T = -14.5, T _D = -12.7 large turbulence.
143745					Out of cloud.
143816	R8 end	FL130			

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B198

Date: 12/05/06 **Operator:** JT **DRS Time:** 07:35:00 **DAU1 Time:** +0 **DAU2 Time:** +0 **DAU3 Time:** -2 **Aux1 Time:** +0 **Aux2 Time:** +0 **Page 1 of 1**

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
10:57:31																T/O All quite on the western front	
11:56:10	148	0.09	3	0		0	0	0	0						0	P1 A FL100	
11:57:31	123	0.09	3	0		0	0	0	0						0	FL110	
11:58:30	60	0.08	3	0		0	0	0	0						0	FL120	
11:			3	75		3	800	700	1000						3	FL130 there were 2 layers	
12:00:45	31	0.08	4	20		2.5	800	50	1000						3	FL150	
12:02:34	37	0.09	4	3		0	0	0	0						0	FL170	
12:03:28	23	0.09	4	0		0	0	0	0						0	FL180	
12:04:24	46	0.08	4	0		0	0	0	0						0	FL190	
12:05:26	36	0.08	4	0		0	0	0	0						0	End of P1 A FL200	
12:07:53																PCASP gone Bimodal in what looks like ch 6 And conc gone too high	
																There be no useful cloud here we be off to wales	
12:26:28	58	0.1	5	100		5	400	500	800						8	P2 D FL200	
12:27:40	46	0.09	5	30		5.5	200	0	0						8	FL190	
12:28:44	112	0.09	5	0		0	0	0	0						0	FL180	
12:29:40	142	0.09	5	3		0	0	0	0						0	FL170	
12:30:37	63	0.08	5	0		0	0	0	0						0	FL160	
12:31:43	102	0.08	5	0		0	0	0	0						0	FL150	
12:32:43	101	0.08	5	0		0	0	0	0						0	FL140	
12:33:45	120	0.09	5	0		0	0	0	0						0	FL130	
12:34:45	116	0.08	5	0		0	0	0	0						0	FL120	
12:35:52	228	0.09	5	0		0	0	0	0						0	FL110	
12:37:09	253	0.09	5	3		0	0	0	0						0	FL100	
12:38:11	412	0.1	5	3		0	0	0	0						0	FL90	
12:39:19	540	0.1	5	0		0	0	0	0						0	FL80	
12:40:26	1237	0.1	5	10		0	0	0	0						0	FL70	
12:41:13	1500	0.1	5	10		0	0	0	0						0	FL60	
12:42:40	1629	0.1	5	10		0	0	0	0						0	FL50	
12:43:30	1555	0.1	5	10		0	0	0	0						0	Interuopt FL40	
12:45:21	1353	0.1	5	8		0	0	0	0						0	Restart FL40	
12:46:33	1461	0.1	5	3		0	0	0	0						0	FL30	
12:47:40	1892	0.1	5	8		0	0	0	0						0	FL20	
12:48:52	3079	0.1	5	15		0	0	0	0						0	End P2 FL10 Start run 1 @ FL10	
12:50:00	2747	0.1	5	10		0	0	0	0						0		
12:52:00	2494	0.1	5	10		0	0	0	0						0		
12:54:00	4728	0.1	5	3		0	0	0	0						0		
12:56:00	1971	0.1	5	8		0	0	0	0						0		
12:58:00	2409	0.1	5	10		0	0	0	0						0		
12:58:51	2511	0.1	6	8		0	0	0	0						0	End run 1 start P3	
13:00:18	2080	0.1	6	5		0	0	0	0						0	FL20	
13:01:20	1709	0.1	6	3		0	0	0	0						0	FL30	
13:02:35	1297	0.1	6	3		0	0	0	0						0	End of P3 FL40	
13:04:10	1601	0.1	6	8		0	0	0	0						0	Start run 2 FL40 out of cloud	
13:06:00	1635	0.1	6	10		0	0	0	0						0	Out of cloud	
13:08:00	1468	0.1	6	3		0	0	0	0						0	Out of cloud	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number: B198****Date:****12/05/2006**

B) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC B198_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data B198_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS	20/06/06	
3) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: B198 b) Path name: MFDDATA:B198_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown e) End time: 240000 if unknown	21/06/06	Problems running this but Manually edited o/p file
4) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: B198 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use, in order of preference, - if a calibration exists after the flight date, then the file that is closest in time to it, - or the most recent calibration file prior to the flight date. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)	N 21/06/06	Note the calibration file used FFSSP_CAL03052006.TXT Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) In PVWAVE a) enter: !path=!path+',mrfb:[pms.proc]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! b) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:B198_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:B198_mfdX','pmsdata:B198_m5procffssp',/auto 1st argument is output file from 5) 2nd argument is the MFD 3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format c) exit	21/06/06	Note the correction applied to FFSSP time by /auto 4 sec manually added to FFSSP time
6) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B198_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:B198_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	21/06/06	
7) CHECKS:		
i) FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC – are they correctly synchronized in time?		Seem to be occasional drop- outs of FFSSP data – zero conc and LWC in cloud on occasions. Occurs throughout flight

ii) If not, may be necessary to repeat 5b) using addt=x keyword. This adds x sec to FFSSP time.		
iii) Alternative at 5b) is to use ,auto=602 or auto=605 to align FFSSP with Nevzorov LWC or TWC.		

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B198

Date:

12/05/2006

C) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer B198.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
2) Zip up file on PC (B198.zip)		
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS		
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B198.zip		
6) In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B198.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] B198_seadas.dat iii) exit		Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written 49189 read, 49188 written 1 bad read
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B198 c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] B198_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data N j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: N l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	105000 155200 20/06/06	Don't worry about lots of FORTRAN run-time errors as long as the program continues. These are format errors when writing to ascii files. Not required Not required
8) 2D image display and printing Quick look at image blocks if required In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B198 c) IWC plot: N d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec Preparation of imagery for Core data product iii) WAVE> auto_image		This section is optional Features to look for: 1) Noise on 2D-P – does it affect non-edge diodes (with potential to create spurious particle counts)? 2) Can you identify a dominant particle habit for the whole flight (eg. drops or crystals) 3)

a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B198 c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks 10 iv) exit PVWAVE Creates files	105000 155200 10	Note some noise in 2DC and badly formed images. FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_B198_2Dx-IMAGES.PS
ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC		
Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter		
Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	20/06/06	Files in O:/CloudPhysics Core data
9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO		If program crashes at a certain Time, for any reason, re-run With that time as the new end.
a) Flight number: B198 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: Hit enter d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:B198_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty h) Start time: Take-off or 0 if unknown i) End time: Landing or 240000 if unknown j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown l) Coefficient choice: 2 m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:B198_PROC2D	0 105000 155200 0.2 8 /8 2 21/06/06	Look for realistic times in Flight Summary file or Cloud Phys operator log. Note the particle type
10) In PVWAVE		Note: This will run quicker if you specify correct start / end times at 9h) and 9j).
i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:B198_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:B198_M5PROC2D' iii) exit	21/06/06	
11) MODIFY		
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B198_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:B198_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	21/06/06	
12) CHECKS:		
i) Is 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC?		Seems OK. Note Nevzorov LWC has a lot of data flagged 2 in later part of flight.

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

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Date:

12/05/2006

E) NetCDF file preparation and ftp to BADC				
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments		
1) Run TAREXEC:MFD_BADC				
For inputs below, just press ENTER to use defaults				
a) MFD to convert: MFDDATA:B198_MFDX b) version number for BADC: r[0] c) Names file: TARDIS_ROOT:[CALTEXT.NETCDF]CP_NAMES.TXT d) Directory: [DATA_ROOT:[NETCDF]] e) File prefix: [core-cloud-phy_faam] f) File suffix: [] g) File for output: [core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B198.nc]	21/06/06	Defaults in [square brackets] As from 4c) above Default NOT the default Default Default default Default name is generated		
2) Ftp transfer to BADC				
- stage 1) creates two files: - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B198.nc - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B198.txt The *.txt file should be renamed to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B198_descrip.txt but this cannot be done on VMS as the filename is too long You should do it if the file is first transferred to a PC, or after it has been uploaded to the appropriate "incoming" directory at BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd /incoming/faam/campaign-processed-core d) copy *.txt file as ascii e) copy *.nc and *2D-IMAGES.pdf files as binary			21/06/06	complete

F) BACKUP PROCEDURES		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Backup the intermediate files created in PMSDATA:		
a) zip "-V" PMSDATA:B198*.* outdir:B198_PMSDATA.zip Note that the uppercase "-V" option is important to preserve the VMS file characteristics when files are restored from this zip file.	21/06/06	Note destination directory "outdir" To CLOUD_PHYS:[BROWN.PMSZIP]

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B198**Date:**

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A) Raw data transfer to BADC		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer raw data files from DVD to PC B198_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data B198_FFSSP_HVMS.txt B198_FFSSP.raw B198_FFSSP_House_1.hse etc.		
2) Zip these file on the PC -output file: core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B198_rawffssp.zip		21/06/06 raw data to BADC from FAAM
3) Transfer SEADAS B198.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
4) Zip up file on PC (B198.zip)		
- rename B198.zip to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B198_rawseadas.zip		
5) ftp to BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd incoming/faam/campaign_raw d) bin e) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B198_rawffssp.zip f) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B198_rawseadas.zip		Binary data transfer

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 198 Date: 12th May 2006

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	Y	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	N
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	N
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	N
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	Y
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	N
J. Williams	Y		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	Y	Racks:	
FWVS	y	INC	N
<u>Radiometers</u>		CCN / CPC	y
Upper Clear	Y	CVI	N
“ Red	Y		
“ Silicon	Y		
“ SHIMS	Y	Aerosol	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	n
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	n
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	N
		AMS	y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
IR Camera			
TAFTS	N		
MARSS	n	Others:	
DEIMOS	n	IR Camera	n
ARIES	n	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	n	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	N
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	N	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	y
ORAC	N	Noxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	N	Tube Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B198

Date: 12th May 2006

Instruments

1. DITM went to full scale during flight when heater turned on – did not recover
2. Turb probe pitot parameter went to 0 drs counts for several minutes
3. Ufc & dfc videos hunt for correct exposure
4. Flight Manager's Laptop – mains lead missing from drawer
5. FM pc crashed twice during flight
6. TWC – status light came on at temperatures less than –25C
7. Fffsssp dropped out when turbulent

Aircraft

Satcom Calls

Nil

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B198:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	pre flight only, unmanned operation on auto calibrate so no In Flight log
CCN	No operator listed but CCN / CPC listed as Y in Flight Managers Inst Status sheet. There is almost certainly no log sheet for CCN.
CVI	No log is ever taken for CVI
CPI	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	26 Sep 2006	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Downward Facing Cameras

3 x Forward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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